

spraying a suspension of 10^8 *Azorhizobium* cells/ml. Control plants were sprayed with sterile distilled water.

Sesbania plants were harvested at 55 DAS. Fresh and dry weight, nodule number, and nodule biomass/plant

were recorded. Nitrogenase activity was measured by the acetylene reduction technique.

Decapitation without inoculation and inoculation without decapitation increased yield parameters (see table). Decapitation followed by inoculation

produced the highest increase. Decapitating young sesbania plants before stem inoculation could maximize N_2 fixation, dry matter production, and N yield. □

Effect of sesbania and azolla on rice grain and straw yields

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We evaluated *Sesbania rostrata*, *S. aculeata*, and *Azolla microphylla* as N sources for rice during 1987-88 dry (Jun-Sep) and wet (Oct-Feb) seasons. The field had moderately drained clay soil (pH 8.2, EC 0.3 dS/m, 288 kg N/ha, 15 kg P/ha, and 526 kg /ha). CO 43 was planted in 1-m² plots. Fresh biomass of *S. rostrata*, *S. aculeata*, and *Azolla microphylla* at 20 t/ha with N content 3.7%, 2.9%, and 2.5% in the dry season and 3.64%, 3.05%, and 2.37% in the wet season, respectively, were incorporated 2 d before planting and allowed to decompose. Prilled

Effect of green manure on rice grain and straw yields. Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)		Straw yield (t/ha)	
	Dry season	Wet season	Dry season	Wet season
Control	2.3	2.8	6.2	6.5
Prilled urea				
60 kg N/ha	2.8	3.2	6.4	6.8
60 kg N/ha + <i>S. rostrata</i>	5.7	6.0	14.0	14.1
60 kg N/ha + <i>S. aculeata</i>	4.4	4.7	12.6	12.8
60 kg N/ha + <i>A. microphylla</i>	3.5	4.0	6.8	7.4
100 kg N/ha	3.7	3.9	7.0	7.3
Neem-coated urea				
60 kg N/ha	3.2	3.7	7.0	7.0
60 kg N/ha + <i>S. rostrata</i>	5.9	6.2	14.4	15.1
60 kg N/ha + <i>S. aculeata</i>	5.0	5.1	13.2	14.3
60 kg N/ha + <i>A. microphylla</i>	3.9	4.5	8.3	9.0
100 kg N/ha	3.9	4.3	8.8	8.8
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.4	0.7	0.9	0.3

urea (PU) and neem-coated prilled urea (NCU) were applied at 60 and 100 kg N/ha, in a random block design with three replications. K and P (50 kg/ha) were basally applied.

S. rostrata and *S. aculeata* with 60 kg N/ha significantly increased grain and straw yields (see table). In all treatments, NCU enhanced yields more than did PU alone. □

Integrated pest management—diseases

Potential antagonist of rice sheath rot (ShR) pathogen

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We studied the antagonistic potential of some phylloplane fungal and bacterial isolates on the growth of rice pathogens *Pyricularia oryzae* Cavara, *Helminthosporium oryzae* Breda de Haan, and *Sarocladium oryzae* Sawada.

Phylloplane isolates of bacteria and fungi obtained from leaf samples taken from healthy plants of seven rice varieties are presented in the table. To test interaction with fungal isolates, the

pathogen and the test organism were placed 4 cm apart on potato-dextrose agar medium in petri plates. To test interaction with bacterial isolates, the pathogen was placed at one end of the

plate and allowed to grow for 3 to 4 d, then the test bacterium was streaked 4 cm from the growing edge of the pathogen colony.

Fungal isolate *Bipolaris zeicola* (Stout) Shoem obtained from IR20 at tillering inhibited mycelial growth of

Population of phylloplane microorganisms in different rice varieties. Coimbatore, India.

Rice variety	Colony-forming units ^a (no./g leaf)			
	Tillering phase		Late boot leaf stage	
	Bacteria × 10 ³	Fungi × 10 ²	Bacteria × 10 ³	Fungi × 10 ²
IR20	24.33	11.33	35.67	12.00
IR50	25.41	11.67	35.67	11.67
CO 43	25.33	11.67	36.00	12.00
ASD16	23.33	12.00	35.00	12.33
IR64	24.67	11.67	35.33	12.33
IR70	24.33	11.33	36.00	13.00
Ponni	25.67	12.60	36.33	13.67

^a Mean of 3 replications.

Inhibition of *S. oryzae* by *B. zeicola*. 1 = *Sarocladium oryzae*, 2 = *Bipolaris zeicola*, 3 = upper colony - *B. zeicola*, lower colony - *S. oryzae*.

S. oryzae in vitro (see figure). A clear inhibition zone was formed between the pathogen and the antagonist. The undiluted culture filtrate of *B. zeicola*

tested on *S. oryzae* completely inhibited mycelial growth of the pathogen. The isolate did not inhibit *P. oryzae* and *H. oryzae*. □

Toxicity of essential oils against *Rhizoctonia solani* Kühn fungus causing sheath blight (ShB) in rice

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We isolated essential oils of *Citrus sinensis*, *Eucalyptus globulus*, *Ocimum*

canum, and *Pinus roxburghii* by hydro-distillation through Clevenger's apparatus and tested their toxicity to *R. solani*, using the classical poisoned food technique.

Because these oils were insoluble in water, desired concentrations were prepared by mixing the requisite amount in 0.5 ml acetone, then mixing that with 14.5 ml sterilized molten PDA medium cooled to 40 °C, in a

sterilized petri plate. Control sets were established by mixing sterilized distilled water in 0.5 ml acetone. All plates were inoculated with a single mycelial disc (5 mm diam) of *R. solani*.

For mycelial dry weight yield, a single mycelial disc of actively growing *R. solani* 5 mm diam was transferred to 100 ml autoclaved and cooled liquid Czapek-Dox + 0.05% yeast extract supplemented with enough of each oil dissolved in 0.5 ml of acetone to get the needed concentration. Medium without oil was the control.

Plates were kept at 26 ± 1 °C. Observations were made after 4 d (radial growth) and 15 d (mycelial dry weight yield).

Growth of the test pathogen was completely inhibited by *O. canum* oil at 0.2% concentration. Oil of *C. sinensis* at the same concentration reduced growth by 87%; oil of *P. roxburghii* by 75.0% (see table).

Mycelial dry weight yield was reduced markedly by oil of *C. sinensis* (to 32 mg compared to 214.0 mg for control).

The inhibitory effects of these oils may be attributed to the presence of some antifungal ingredients in the oil. Several antifungal properties of higher plants, in the form of volatile or nonvolatile compounds, have already been demonstrated against *Aspergillus* sp., *Fusarium* sp., *Macrophomina phaseolina*, and *Sclerotium rolfsii*. Natural products, such as protoanemonin, allamandoside, and essential oils of *O. canum*, also have been known to be more effective than synthetic fungicides. The products of higher plants that have shown antifungal activity may be useful to control ShB in rice. □

Toxicity of essential oils to *Rhizoctonia solani*.

Plant oil	Concentration (%)	Growth inhibition ^a (%)	Mycelial dry wt yield ^b (mg)	Sclerotia production ^b (% reduction)
<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	0.05	47.8	134.5 ± 2.65	61.2 ± 2.04
	0.10	54.5	124.1 ± 2.53	13.7 ± 3.38
	0.15	76.1	60.6 ± 2.78	89.1 ± 4.22
	0.20	87.0	32.0 ± 2.09	92.6 ± 3.86
<i>Eucalyptus globulus</i>	0.05	28.3	182.6 ± 2.44	56.4 ± 3.91
	0.10	47.5	126.3 ± 2.89	69.5 ± 3.59
	0.15	53.9	112.1 ± 2.77	76.2 ± 2.14
	0.20	59.2	89.3 ± 1.91	81.0 ± 1.46
<i>Ocimum canum</i>	0.05	53.2	105.0 ± 2.72	74.0 ± 2.19
	0.10	64.8	92.3 ± 3.18	87.5 ± 1.45
	0.15	91.1	25.3 ± 1.96	96.0 ± 1.26
	0.20	100	0	0
<i>Pinus roxburghii</i>	0.05	35.2	157.3 ± 2.94	49.6 ± 3.69
	0.10	47.8	125.6 ± 2.12	57.0 ± 2.52
	0.15	52.6	114.6 ± 2.88	65.7 ± 1.94
	0.20	75.0	62.6 ± 2.44	84.6 ± 1.29
Control	—	—	214.0 ± 2.94	—

^aEach figure represents the average of 3 determinations. ^bEach value is the mean of 3 replications, ± standard error. All oils tested were toxic at higher concentrations. *Ocimum canum* at 0.20% concentration completely inhibited mycelial growth.

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